

INCIDENCE, EVOLUTION AND REPERCUSSIONS OF HYPODERMOSIS IN RUMINANTS IN MOUNTAIN HABITATS

Doru NECULA^{1,2}

¹ National Institute of Economic Research "Costin C. Kirişescu", Centre of Mountain Economy CE-MONT, Petreni no. 49, 725700, Vatra Dornei, Romania

² Department of Physiology, University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine, Manăştur Street, no. 3–5, 400037, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

Corresponding author: sv63dor@yahoo.com

Abstract

At the present time, the progress in veterinary medicine gives us the classification of many diseases with a high incidence in mountain areas and respectively with considerable economic consequences brought to cattle breeders in mountain areas. One of these diseases that develops especially in the Carpathian and Subcarpathian areas of Romania is Hypodermosis. This disease evolves in many areas of the world. In our country, it evolves with a much higher incidence in the hill and mountain areas and a lower incidence in the south of the country. It causes significant damage from an economic point of view in the leather industry, by reducing milk production by more than 10% and weakening animals with a low yield at slaughter, as well as from a sanitary-veterinary point of view with their recovery costs. At this moment in Romania, thanks to the measures to combat and prevent, the prevalence decreased in 2023 to a percentage of 0.31%.

Keywords: Hypodermosis ; cattle; mountain areas; prevalence; economic; production.

INTRODUCTION

Hypodermosis is a chronic cutaneous myiasis that evolves seasonally, produced by the larvae of the Genus *Hypoderma*, which are located subcutaneously, and give rise to nodules in the dorsal-lumbar region. The disease is popularly known as "pimples" and is spread all over the globe (Şuteu and Cozma, 2004). Warble flies (*Hypoderma* sp.) are common pests of cattle in the Northern Hemisphere. Cattle infested with their fly larvae suffer severe damage to the subcutaneous connective tissue, skin, and sometimes even death from toxemia or anaphylactic shock, or even damage to the central nervous system (CNS). Also during the larval stages, they produce enzymes that can cause immunosuppression and manifestations of some secondary diseases (Boulard et al., 1997). The development of this disease influences the decrease in milk production and weight loss in the young (Tarry, 1986).

MATERIALS AND RESEARCH METHOD

This work as a whole highlights one of the main conditions that evolves in bulls from mountain areas with major repercussions from an economic and veterinary medical point of view. In this sense, I studied domestic and international specialist literature which I updated to the Motan specifics, together with my knowledge and practice as a veterinary practitioner for over 30 years in the mountain area of the Dornelor Basin. Through this work, even if these aspects are known, I wanted to bring to the attention of taurine breeders

the implications from a medical point of view and repercussions from an economic point of view, in order to try as much as possible to prevent the occurrence of this condition.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

a. Etiology

Hypoderma evolves with 2 important etiological agents: *Hypodema bovis* and *Hypoderma lineatum*, which lead a parasitic life in the L1., L2., and L3. stages, and the adults, pupae and nymphs are not parasitic.

b. Biological cycle

Hypoderma adults mate during the short life span of 7–14 days. Females of *Hippoderma bovis* (Fig.1) lay their eggs in flight, isolated on the hairs on the sides of the neck, sable, lower thoraco-abdominal region of the animals (Dulceanu and Terente, 1994).

Fig. 1. *Hypoderma bovis* fly (Oestridae, Hypodermatinae), adult female

Source: Scholl et al, 2019

Those of *Hypoderma lineata* deposit them in groups on the hairs (Fig.2) on the sallow and on the sides of the neck (Şuteu and Cozma, 2004).

Fig. 2. Eggs of *Hypoderma lineatum* (Oestridae, Hypodermatinae), attached to hairs

Source: Scholl et al, 2019

A female can lay 200–800 eggs in a very short interval (Şuteu and Cozma, 2004). After approximately 4–6 days of incubation on the skin, they hatch into L1 larvae, which at the base of the hair penetrate deep into the skin and migrate into the connective tissue (Boulard, 2002). Larvae L1. of *Hypoderma bovis* from the subcutaneous connective tissue, some migrate into the spinal canal through the conjugation holes, others into the pleural and abdominal cavity, through the dorsal musculature (Şuteu and Cozma, 2004). The migration takes place in an interval of 5–6 months. Beesley, (1962) also found L1 larvae in the central nervous system (CNS). From a few larvae to more than 100 were discovered in the spinal canal (Şuteu and Cozma, 2004). Some of the larvae are destroyed, disintegrate or qualify. The highest incidence in the medullary canal is in the months of November to May, but they are most common in the months of January to February (Beesley, 1962). In the February–March periods, in mountain areas even in April, the larvae penetrate the tissues up to the dorso-lumbar region and perforate the skin transforming into L2 stage larvae (Weintraub, 1961). In the case of *Hypoderma liniata* larvae, they cross the skin directly between the hairs or at the level of the opening of the hair follicle, after which they migrate. According to Nelson, and Weintraub, (1972) only 10–15% of L1 larvae will become L3 larvae (Fig.3). In this variety, the L1 larvae stay for about 5 months in the esophagus, from where they then migrate to the dorso-lumbar region (Şuteu and Cozma, 2004). According to some authors (Dinulescu and Niculescu, 1960; Hadwen, and Fulton, 1924) the larvae can also enter through the mouth when the animal licks, it picks up the L1 larvae, from the level of the hair, from where it migrates through the esophagus to the dorso-lumbar region. L1 larvae turn into L2, then after a period of about two months, during which they feed on secretions and pus, they turn into L3, which lasts about 1.5–2 months.

Fig. 3. Larvae, *Hypoderma* sp. (Oestridae, Hypodermatinae), of L3 cs, cross section of *H. bovis*; ps1, larvae of (*H. bovis*), L3; ps2 , *H. lineatum* larvae, L3

Source: Scholl et al, 2019

After this period, they become mature, detach through the holes in the skin and fall to the ground, where they pupate, the stage lasting 25–30 days, at a temperature of 25–29°C or about two months at a lower temperature (Dulceanu and Terente, 1994). This phase is followed by the emergence of adults that resume their cycle.

c. Epidemiology

Taurines are contaminated from June to September. Egg laying by female hypodermic occurs during the day accompanied by a characteristic noise and causes behavioral reactions in cattle. They attack pastures (*Hypoderma bovis*) or paddocks (*Hypoderma lineata*) and fly in search of animals up to 5 km (Șuteu and Cozma, 2004). No cases of hypodermosis were found in bulls kept in stables. From a clinical point of view, the manifestations appear from February and continue until summer. Cattle are the most susceptible, but sporadically it can also occur in horses. The young in the first year of grazing are most susceptible, then until the age of 3 years they continue to get the disease. Adult coils only do sporadically, their resistance being due to post-infestation immune background. The disease occurs more frequently in the hilly and mountainous regions of the Subcarpathians and plateaus, because the ecological conditions in these areas favor the development of insects. In drier areas such as the south of the country, the incidence is much lower.

d. Pathogenesis

The main form of pathogenic action is due to trauma and perforation of the skin for the migration of L1 and later L2 larvae, which in order to breathe form holes on the surface of the skin (Fig.4). The saliva and excretions (a hypodermotoxin) released by the larvae produce a traumatic irritant and histolytic effect. During migration, the larvae create pathways through which they transport bacterial germs such as: *Clostridium chauveii*, *Clostridium aedematiens* (Normand et al., 1979) which can cause hemorrhagic and inflammatory processes in the esophagus, muscles and subcutaneous abscesses in the dorso-lumbar region (Fig.4).

Fig. 4. Multiple warble subcutaneous abscesses along the dorsal region of cattle caused by *Hypoderma bovis* (Oestridae, Hypodermatinae)

Source: Scholl et al, 2019

During the evolution of L2 and L3, chronic granulomatous reactions occur, forming a nodule in the subcutaneous connective tissue. At the intraspinal level, the dead larvae release proteolytic enzymes causing medullary necrosis and during the migration of the live larvae, they have a compressive, medullary effect, producing edema and intraspinal hemorrhages (Rivas, 2010). Larvae of all stages, through the degradation of dead specimens, have antigenic

properties inducing the formation of specific antibodies (Robertson, 1980). If a large number of larvae are destroyed, anaphylactic shock can occur through manual interventions, due to the release of antigenic complexes in large numbers (Romaniuk, 1973).

e. Immunity

In hypodermosis, a state of post-infested immunity always occurs (Robertson, 1980; Boulard, et al., 1996) in which, right from the first migration stage of the larvae, they are received by the immunofforming mechanisms and thus anti-larval antibodies are formed, easily detectable at two months postinfection or 260–295 days postinfestation (Șuteu and Cozma, 2004; Robertson, 1980). When flies infest taurines in waves, with the appearance of L1, there is an increase in circulating antibodies with the destruction of some larvae.

f. Symptomatology

During the flight of the hypoderms, due to the noise they make, the animals become restless and cannot feed, they retreat to shelter or near running water (if any) because in these areas they do not attack. During these attacks the animals are agitated and their milk production decreases. The main pathognomonic sign that appears the following year, starting from January-February, is the appearance of hypodermic nodules that appear on the dorsolumbar region. At first, the nodules are the size of a grain of corn and reach the size of a walnut, and in large infestations they may also appear on the chest or rump. In inflammatory and medullary hemorrhagic processes, paresis and paraplegia can occur that are difficult to diagnose clinically. At the hole of the nodules on the surface of the skin by drying the secretions, crusts form. When an overinfestation occurs and with the destruction of the larvae, an abscess is formed with purulent secretions. After the L3 larvae hatch, involution and scarring of the lesions occurs. When strong infestations occur, the animals lose weight, losing about 15–20 kg/animal. In the case of esophagitis, swallowing disorders occur with the lack of prestomach peristalsis and difficulty in rumination. The most serious complications are obstructive esophagitis and the production of anaphylactic shock. The prevalence of Warble Flies varies greatly depending on the region (Dărăbuș et al., 2023). Studies by some Romanian researchers highlight the prevalence of the disease in two distinct areas, in the south of the country with a prevalence in 2005 between 32 and 43% (Cozma et al 1995) and in the north-east of the country in 2023 of 0.31% (Dărăbuș et al, 2023). This difference can also be explained due to the climatic differences between the southern part of the country with higher temperatures and the northern part with lower temperatures, the southern part having more favorable conditions for the evolution of warble flies (Dărăbuș et al., 2023).

g. Diagnostic

The diagnosis is easy to establish from a clinical point of view through a simple examination of the dorsolumbar region, where we will easily notice the nodules formed or in the process of formation, in the winter to spring season. The diagnosis is certain and cannot be confused with any other condition. Thus, any cattle breeder can establish this.

h. Prognosticate

From a medical point of view, this is favorable except in cases of paresis, paraplegia, or anaphylactic shock when the prognosis becomes reserved. From an economic point of

view, the disease brings major damages through the depreciation of skins with hypodermic nodules in slaughtered bulls. Also, in youth the decrease and lack of weight gain, and in adult females the decrease in milk production by 40–60%.

i. Treatment

Current therapy benefits from a series of larvicidal substances with injectable or local application. Ivermectin is very effective against all larval stages of hypoderm. After the fly season is over (September), cattle should be treated as soon as possible. In order to achieve the desired results, the treatment consists of injecting the animals with drugs based on ivermectin, avermectin or doramectin, in doses of 0.2 mg/kg body weight. A new treatment will be administered during the winter for internal and external parasitosis, thus destroying any larvae responsible for hypoderma. Local applications for combating insects are made throughout the summer with cypermethrin or butox solution, applied to the dorso-lumbar region.

Prophylactic treatments. Prevention measures focus on the use of the same drugs used in the prepatent period when the larvae begin to migrate into the body, corresponding to November. The prophylactic methods instituted in this larval migration phase present spectacular advantages due to the relief of suffering, but also the prevention of economic losses.

j. Preventive measures

By using ivermectin in nematode infestations, in young cattle up to 3 months high efficacy is also obtained in *Hypoderma* sp. (Drummond, 1984; Boulard, et al., 2008), thus providing high protection. Great attention should be paid to purchased cattle that require prophylactic treatment from the first moment (O'Brien, 1998). Also, a prophylactic and very effective treatment administered in the autumn at low costs, can be used in the form of a microdose, of 2 µg/kg, of "Ivomec" which is also non-threatening to the environment (Boulard, et al., 2008). This strategy, practiced for a long time in France, began to be successfully practiced in our country as well during the autumn mass prophylactic actions, which are carried out on animals according to the "National Program of Actions for the Surveillance, Prevention, Control and Eradication of Diseases in animals".

Fighting adult insects is possible by spraying the whole body of bulls with insecticides during grazing, applied against fleas, lice, and scabies, which also have an anti-hypodermic effect. In recent years, thanks to preventive measures and ivermectin treatments, applied to animals to prevent parasitic diseases, there has been a significant decrease in these diseases even to the point of their eradication (Dărăbus et al., 2023) such as Great Britain where from a population of 10 million cattle before eradication, the prevalence was 40% (Hassan et al., 2010). And in other countries the prevalence has decreased in recent years: Greece 37.4% (Papadopoulos, 2004) in Poland 16%, Switzerland 20% (Yin et al., 2010), Albania 31% (Otranto et al., 2005).

k. Economic implications

From an economic point of view, the disease can cause important losses. The biggest losses for farmers in the mountain area come from reduced milk production. Also in the growing youth and fattening the decrease in weight gain and in the slaughtered animals, the

depreciation of the carcasses and the loss of the skins. Considering the prevalence and the economic losses that Hypodermosis brings to farmers in the mountain area, an accounting analysis of the losses should be taken into account and drawn up, with the estimation of a benefit-cost ratio and the application of investment strategies with the research.

CONCLUSION

Concluding the aspects presented in this paper, a series of warnings and sustainable measures can be formulated for farmers in mountain areas.

Hypodermosis is a chronic, benign disease with seasonal evolution produced by Hypoderma larvae with subcutaneous localization, a disease popularly known as "pimples" that mostly affects cattle. It is specific to all northern regions, but more pronounced in the hill and mountain areas, being favored by the climatic conditions specific to these areas that ensure the evolution of this parasite. The life cycle of the parasite is approximately one year, of which 9 months are spent in animals as internal parasites and the rest of the time in the external environment. It has a high degree of infestation in cattle and generally a high prevalence throughout the grazing period. Untreated animals represent a true reservoir of re-infestation of the disease for the healthy ones. It causes significant economic damage in the leather industry, as well as by decreasing milk production and depreciating meat at slaughter. Hypodermosis represents a great global threat, especially for the northern area, for clinically healthy animals, also producing a serious impact from an economic point of view. Thanks to the preventive measures instituted in recent years for parasitic diseases in animals with the product "Ivermectin", the prevalence of hypodermosis in the northern areas of the globe has decreased considerably, including in Romania reaching a percentage of only 0.31% in 2023.

It is necessary to implement and organize continuous education programs for farmers, a more careful awareness and approach regarding the dynamics and evolution of hypodermosis in cattle in mountainous areas.

By implementing these forms of continuous education, farmers could also become aware of the evolution of some diseases with economic impact, specific to mountain areas.

AUTHOR(S) CONTRIBUTION

Not applicable.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD STATEMENT

Not applicable.

INFORMED CONSENT STATEMENT

Not applicable.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Not applicable.

REFERENCES

- Beesley W.N.** (1962). Observations on the development of *Hypoderma bovis* de Geer (Diptera, Oestridae) in the bovine host. *Research in Veterinary Science*, 3(2), 203–208.
- Beesley W.N.** (1974). Arthropods–Oestridae, Myiases and acarines. In *Proceedings of the... International conference*.
- Boulard C.** (2002). Durably controlling bovine hypodermosis. *Veterinary Research*, 33(5), 455–464.
- Boulard C., Alvinerie M., Argenté G., Languille J., Paget L., & Petit E.** (2008). A successful, sustainable and low cost control-programme for bovine hypodermosis in France. *Veterinary parasitology*, 158(1–2), 1–10.
- Boulard C., Villejoubert C., & Moiré N.** (1996). Antigeni reactivi încrucișați, specifici etapelor din familia Oestridae. *Cercetare veterinară*, 27 (4–5), 535–544.
- Colebrook Ellen; Wall Richard.** Ectoparasites of livestock in Europe and the Mediterranean region. *Veterinary Parasitology*, 2004, 120.4: 251–274.
- Cozma V., Suteu E.** Epidemiology and Aetiology of Bovine Hypodermosis in Northwestern Romania. In: Tarry DW, Pithan K, Webster K, editors. *Improvements in control methods for Warble-Fly in cattle and goats*. Commission of the European Communities; Brussels, Belgium: 1995. pp. 65–68.
- Dărăbuș G., Lupu M.A., Mederle N., Dărăbuș R.G., Imre K., Mederle O., ... & Olariu T.R.** (2023). Epidemiology of *Cryptosporidium* infection in Romania: a review. *Microorganisms*, 11(7), 1793.
- Dărăbuș G., Tomoiogă V.D., Florea T., Imre M., Oprescu I., Morariu S., ... & Ilie, M.S.** (2023). Epidemiological Surveillance of Hypodermosis in Cattle from Romania. *Pathogens*, 12(9), 1077.
- Dalton J.P.** Fasciolosis. Wallingford, Oxon, UK: CABI Pub., 465–525.
- Dinulescu G., Niculescu A.** (1960). *Parazitologie clinica veterinară*.
- Drummond R.O.** (1984). Control of larvae of the common cattle grub (Diptera: Oestridae) with animal systemic insecticides. *Journal of economic entomology*, 77(2), 402–406.
- Dulceanu N., Terinte C.** (1994). *Parazitologie veterinară*. Ed. Moldova, Iași, 2.
- Hadwen S., Fulton, J.S.** (1924). On the migration of *Hypoderma lineatum* from the skin to the gullet. *Parasitology*, 16(1), 98–106.
- Haine D., Boelaert F., Pfeiffer D.U., Saegerman C., Lonneux J.F., Losson B., & Mintiens K.** (2004). Herd-level seroprevalence and risk-mapping of bovine hypodermosis in Belgian cattle herds. *Preventive veterinary medicine*, 65(1–2), 93–104.
- Hassan M.U., Khan M.N., Abubakar M., Waheed H.M., Iqbal Z., & Hussain M.** (2010). Bovine hypodermosis—a global aspect. *Tropical animal health and production*, 42, 1615–1625.
- Nelson W.A., Weintraub J.** (1972). *Hypoderma lineatum* (De Vill.) (Diptera: Oestridae): invasion of the bovine skin by newly hatched larvae. *The Journal of Parasitology*, 614–624.
- Norman, J.O., Younger R.L.** (1979). Microbial flora of *Hypoderma* (Diptera: Oestridae) larvae taken from cattle treated with juvenile hormone analogues. *Journal of Medical Entomology*, 16(1), 43–47.
- O'Brien D.J.** (1998). Warble fly prevalence in Europe 1997 after COST 811. Boulard C, Sol J, O'Brien D, Webster K, Sampimon OC, editors. COST, 811.
- Otranto D., Zalla P., Testini G., & Zanaj S.** (2005). Cattle grub infestation by *Hypoderma* sp. in Albania and risks for European countries. *Veterinary parasitology*, 128(1–2), 157–162.
- Papadopoulos E.** Hipodermoza în Grecia. *Bărbie. J. Vet. Parazitol.* 2004; 12 :20–23.
- Rivas V.D.** (2010). Respuesta celular cutánea y producción de citoquinas como factores determinantes de protección en la infestación por *Hypoderma* sp. *Univ Santiago de Compostela*.

- Robertson R.H.** (1980). Antibody production in cattle infected with *Hypoderma* spp. *Canadian Journal of Zoology*, 58(2), 245–251.
- Romaniuk K.** (1973). Studies on pathogenesis of hypodermatosis in cattle. I. Changes in hemogram, serum protein and the body weight of heifers in the complete cycle of infection with *Hypoderma bovis* (de Geer, 1776) larvae. *Acta parasitologica polonica*.
- Tarry D.W.** (1986). Progress in warble fly eradication. *Parasitology Today*, 2(4), 111–116.
- Scholl P.J., Colwell D.D., & Cepeda-Palacios R.** (2019). Myiasis (Muscoidea, Oestroidea). In *Medical and veterinary entomology* (pp. 383–419). Academic Press.
- Weintraub J.** (1961). Inducing mating and oviposition of the warble flies *Hypoderma bovis* (L.) and *H. lineatum* (De Vill.) (Diptera: Oestridae) in captivity. *The Canadian Entomologist*, 93(2).
- Spithill T.W., Smooker P.M., Copeman D.B.,** 1999. "Fasciola gigantica: epidemiology, control, immunology and molecular biology". In Dalton, J.P. *Fasciolosis*. Wallingford, Oxon, UK: CABI Pub., 465–525.
- Şuteu I., Cozma V.** (2004). *Parazitologie clinică veterinară: Parazitologie generală, protozooze, trematodoze și cestodoze*. Risoprint.
- Yin H., Miling H., Gailing H., Haung S., Zheijie L., Jiaxutn L., Guiquan G.** Hypodermosis in China; Proceedings of the INCO Conference; Athens, Greece. 9–10 June 2010.